

Assessing the Role of Morticulture in biodiversity conservation in Bangladesh

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Research Article

Keywords: Morticulture, deadwood, biodiversity conservation, mammals, amphibians, birds in Bangladesh

Posted Date: May 10th, 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2901827/v1>

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Abstract

Deadwood plays a critical role in the functioning of forest ecosystems and maintaining biodiversity. The deadwood in the forests of Bangladesh is almost absent due to the scarcity of fuelwood. On the other hand, biodiversity loss occurs in Bangladesh at an alarming rate. The study aimed to assess how deadwood can enrich biodiversity in Bangladesh. Based on the respondents' perceptions, it was revealed that deadwood conservation in the natural habitats can increase the abundance of chickadees, Streak-breasted Woodpecker, Fairy bluebirds, leafbirds, common kestrels, magpie robins, Bay woodpeckers, Chestnut-bellied Nuthatch, etc. The endangered small mammals and amphibians can be increased through morticulture. Simultaneously, the decayed deadwood adds organic matter to the forest soil which in turn promotes the natural succession of many plant species. With the support of the key informants, approaches for deadwood conservation in Bangladesh were developed.

Introduction

American scientist, Harmon (2001) named his field of study on deadwood "*morticulture*" and described the importance of managing the dead trees in the forests to enrich biodiversity. Deadwood plays a critical role in the functioning of forest ecosystems and maintaining of biodiversity (Bauhus et al. 2018; Ferro 2018; Stokland et al. 2004; Vítková et al. 2018; Ranius & Fahrig 2006; Lassauce et al. 2011; Seibold et al. 2015; Humphrey et al. 2005). Deadwood is an indicator that describes the level of naturalness and became a general reference for natural forests (Petit et al. 2008; Čosović et al. 2020; Lombardi et al. 2015; Rahman et al. 2008). Deadwood is an important indicator that determines '*hemeroby*' or the degree of naturalness of a habitat (Frank & Müller 2003; McRoberts et al. 2012; Winter 2012; Hill et al. 2002; Rossi et al. 2018, Rahman 2023a).

Vacik et al. (2009) defined standing deadwood as snag while downed dead trees as logs. Both snag and log play a significant role in the ecosystem processes like providing habitat for small animals, seedbeds for plant establishment, and storage of carbon (Măciucă 2012; Evans 2011; Lambert et al. 2016; Burdette & Schuster 2007; Tedersoo et al. 2008). Stokland et al. (2012) reported that about 25% of forest biodiversity is dependent on deadwood as a place to live and as a source of food. The deadwood in the forests of Bangladesh is almost absent due to the scarcity of fuelwood (Rahman 2009; Rahman et al. 2009; Rahman & Vacik 2009). In European natural forests, deadwood is about 7% of the volume of living trees (Neumann et al. 2016; Zianis et al. 2005; Jenkins 2004). Biodiversity loss occurs in Bangladesh at an alarming rate (Mukul et al. 2018; Mukul 2007; Rahman 2015; Miah et al. 2023; Uddin et al. 2023; Reza & Hasan 2019, Alauddin et al. 2020; Rahman 2023b; Rahman 2022 a, b; Rahman 2021 a, b, c). The study aimed to assess how deadwood can enrich the biodiversity in Bangladesh and to outline deadwood conservation.

Methodology

This study used mainly primary data. The secondary data were reviewed to understand the role of deadwood in biodiversity conservation. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders like foresters, wildlife specialists, and conservation specialists. A total number of 10 key informants were interviewed to develop deadwood conservation approaches for Bangladesh. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

Results and Discussions

How deadwood can enrich biodiversity in Bangladesh?

Birds

The respondents opined that deadwood provides nesting for birds. They added that small dead trees are the habitat of chickadees, Streak-breasted woodpeckers, Fairy bluebirds, leafbirds, etc. The medium dead tree provides shelter for common kestrel, magpie robin, Bay woodpecker, Chestnut-bellied Nuthatch, etc. Different types of woodpeckers and owls live in the large dead tree. Generally, small-standing deadwood is the favourite habitat of foraging birds and small cavity nesters.

Woodpeckers are the primary cavity excavators, which cannot live in the forests without the presence of standing dead trees. The raptors use the standing dead tree as perches. On the other hand, some birds use the secondary cavity for nesting. The lying deadwood serves important habitat for insectivorous birds. The respondents recommended morticulture in the Sal Forest, Hill Forest and Sundarbans mangrove to preserve the deadwood for halting the further decline of these birds. Different studies showed the abundance of Birds in Bangladesh is declining due to habitat loss (Bird et al. 2010; Galib et al. 2018; Chowdhury et al. 2023; Hasan *et al.* 2023; Jahan et al. 2022; Zoeckler et al. 2010).

Mammals and amphibians

The respondents opined that cavity-dependent mammals like bats, pangolins, rodents, shrews, etc. use bird's cavities for shelter, nest sites and the rearing of the child. Salamanders also live in the dead tree. They use dead trees for feeding, foraging, and protection from thermal drought. Amphibians such as toads and frogs live in the lying deadwood to protect them from thermal drought and predators. The small mammals and amphibians (Mukul et al. 2018; Reza & Hasan 2019; Rahman et al. 2019). The respondents stressed deadwood culture in the natural habitats to enrich the abundance of small mammals and amphibians.

Flora

The respondents noted that lying deadwood supplies moisture and nutrients to the soil and encourages growth, which, in turn, promotes the natural succession of the plant species in the forest. They added that deadwood reduces soil erosion, stores nutrients and preserves water. It was argued that deadwood provides a congenial growing medium for various species of bryophytes, lichens, and fungi. Mushroom has the highest diversity on the decayed deadwood.

Deadwood conservation approaches in Bangladesh

Keeping the deadwood on the forest floor after harvesting

The removal of the deadwood following harvesting should be stopped. From a wildlife habitat point of view, a few deadwood is better than none and more is better than some. The size of a dead-standing tree is important, as the larger animal cannot use a small dead tree. Leaving a single dead tree erupts competition among the users. It is better to keep clumps of deadwood in a scattered ways so that small mammals and amphibians can protect themselves from predators. It is also important to maintain a balance between standing and lying dead trees. The respondents suggested preserving deadwood which is at least 5% of the total volume of wood.

Other initiatives

- Providing a guideline for the Forest Department
- Educating forest users
- Enforcing the guideline
- Creating public awareness
- Emphasizing active restoration measures
- Incorporating into national biodiversity strategies and national forest programme
- Supporting and collaborating with research projects which aim at quantifying the biodiversity values of deadwood

Declaration

The author declares that the participants consented to participate in the interviews and to publish this study.

Conflict of Interests: There is no conflict of interest in this manuscript.

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